

The Relation between the Organizational Trust Level and Organizational Justice Perceptions of Staff in Konya Municipality: A Theoretical and Empirical Study

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Abstract—The aim of the study is to determine the relationship between organizational trust level and organizational justice of Municipality officials. Correlational method has been used via descriptive survey model and Organizational Justice Perception Scale, Organizational Trust Inventory and Interpersonal Trust Scale have been applied to 353 participants who work in Konya Metropolitan Municipality and central district municipalities in the study. Frequency as statistical method, Independent Samples t test for binary groups, One Way-ANOVA analyses for multi-groups and Pearson Correlation analysis have been used to determine the relation in the data analysis process.

It has been determined in the outcomes of the study that participants have high level of organizational trust, “Interpersonal Trust” is in the first place and there is a significant difference in the favor of male officials in terms of Trust on the Organization Itself and Interpersonal Trust. It has also been understood that officials in district municipalities have higher perception level in all dimensions, there is a significant difference in Trust on the Organization sub-dimension and work status is an important factor on organizational trust perception. Moreover, the study has shown that organizational justice implementations are important in raising trust of official on the organization, administrator and colleagues, and there is a parallel relation between Organizational Trust components and Organizational Trust dimensions.

Keywords—Konya, Organizational Justice, Organizational.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE rise in environmental and economic changes, the high necessity of flexibility and cooperation, the rise of belief in team and team work, the change of relations with employees and career forms have highlighted the importance of organizational justice. Trust, which is the main element of social capital, is the key bound holding relations together in an organization. It is not possible for an institution to achieve goals and run well without trust. Additionally, trust is one of the important factors of efficient relations. Mutual trust is a vital situation. To be able to benefit from positive results of intra organizational trust it is needed to understand concept and structure of organizational trust in detail [1].

Organizational justice is one of the main sources of trust. Perceptions of employees for their organizations’ implementations affect their commitment and trust on their administrators [1].

According to Brockner et al. organizational trust is directly

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related to organizational justice perception and useful in understanding transactional relation between organizational justice dimensions [2].

One of the significant factors that should be focused on to achieve targeted aims by organizations is the staff. Staff is one of the important factors to create public’s satisfaction for services and to standardize the quality of the service especially in municipalities where administrative staff and decision making bodies are determined by elections.

Main factors affecting the level of achieving targeted goals, in other saying success level of organizations are such psychological factors as trust, justice, commitment, and satisfaction, motivation [3], Özen, Hoy and Tarter see organization justice as a key in organizational trust and organizational justice affects organizational trust directly, and organizational input and outputs of these two terms related to human must be established so that organizational outputs of terms can be positive [4]-[6].

Taking these facts into consideration, it is aimed to determine organizational trust level of staff and then analyze the relation between organizational trust and organizational justice perception.

II. ORGANIZATIONAL TRUST

The term “trust” which is described as commitment without any worry, avoidance and fear by Turkish Language Association is addressed both by ourselves and by others around us in every phase of our lives and it is based on honesty and truth. Therefore, trust reflects of an individual’s positive expectations from others around him [7]. Most sociologist, economist, psychologist and administrative researchers have an agreement that trust is an important factor in constructing and sustaining inter personal relations [1].

Organizational trust can be defined as network of behaviors and organizational relations stemming from the trust of members on the organization and administrators in organizational relations and interactions [8].

Organizational trust is a fundamental element for the effectiveness of organizations [9]. It is not possible to claim that there are reliable organizational communications between members of the organization and their administrators, information sharing, organizational performance, participation, sharing and organizational effectiveness in organizations lacking of organizational trust [10].

Because of its intangible essence, trust concept which can be specified through feelings involves an emotional

commitment representing a sincere interest for individuals and is defined by various perspectives from different disciplines. Organizational trust deals with employer and organization aspects of trust relationship based on employee [7].

Intra organizational trust can be defined as the ambience of trust occurring in the organization and favorable expectations developing out of organizational roles, relations and experience about intentions and behavior of individuals. Studies on organizational trust have mostly focused on 3 points: interpersonal trust, trust in the organization and trust on administration. In other words, trust arises in both individual and organization level [11].

III. ORGANIZATIONAL JUSTICE

In the general sense, organizational justice is the reflection of justice perception to workplace, that is to say, it is justice perception related to workplace. Organizational justice have been looked into three dimensions in the related literature [12]-[14]; distributive, operative and transactional. Distributive justice describes employees' perceptions against whether acquisitions and rewards are distributed justly.

In other words, distributive justice is perceptions about whether acquisitions of employees are evaluated properly and truly in terms of their performance [6], Yıldırım, explains organizational justice as rules and social norms concerning how rewards and punishments are managed and distributed in organizations [15].

These rules and social norms are standards concerning inter personal implementations, how rewards and punishments are distributed, and how some distribution decisions are made.

IV. TRUST AND ORGANIZATIONAL JUSTICE

Organizational justice perception is affected by politics through organizational and administrative implementations in general. In other saying, trust feeling of employees on their organization and administrator affects directly their justice perception for their organization positively [16].

The existence of justice in an organization is possible with trust and citizenship feeling, as for organizational dimension; it becomes possible with high efficiency, favorable workplace environment and strong organizational culture [17].

Deficiency of organizational justice results in distrust of employees on other employees and administrators of the organization and not seeing themselves as a member of the organization.

V. DATA ANALYSIS

A. Method

In this study, the relation between organizational trust feelings and organizational justice perceptions has been compared in terms of different variables according to perceptions of staff working in Konya Metropolitan Municipality, Meram, Karatay and Selçuklu District Municipalities in 2013. For this reason, a descriptive method in general scanning model has been preferred. Sample group consists of 353 participants picked out of 6255 staffs

randomly.

B. Data Collection Techniques

Personal Information Form, Organizational Justice Perception Scale, Organizational Trust Inventory and Interpersonal Trust Scale have been used with a view to collect data.

Organizational Justice Perception Scale developed by Colquitt [18], adapted into Turkish by Özmen, Arbak and Özer is made of 20 questions and four sub-dimensions [19]. Cronbach Alpha values have been found 94 for distributive justice perception dimension, 86 for operative justice perception dimension and 88 for transactional justice perception dimension.

Organizational Trust Scale: Organizational Trust Inventory which was developed by Nyhan and Marlowe (1997) to measure trust on administrator and on organization itself and made of 12 statements has been used. The rate of participants' participation in these statements has been measured by a 5 point likert scale. Reliability coefficients of Cronbach's Alpha have been determined as $(\alpha) = 0.93$ for trust on administrator dimension and $(\alpha) = 0.85$ for trust on organization itself [20].

Interpersonal Trust Scale: Interpersonal Trust Scale developed by Cook and Wall [21] and made of 6 statements takes original Alpha reliability coefficients as 0.85-0.91, while it has been determined 0.87 in studies in Turkey [20].

VI. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

It has been determined that staff perceptions for "Interpersonal Trust" has the first place ($\bar{X} = 4.06$) compared to other dimensions of the scale in Table I. The staffs' perceptions for "Trust on Administrator" is $\bar{X} = 3.99$, and for "Trust on the Organization Itself" is $\bar{X} = 3.59$.

It has been concluded that regarding perception level of the staff, Interpersonal trust is higher while Trust on the Organization Itself is lower.

When organizational trust dimension analyzed on the gender variable basis, there can be seen a significant difference in "Trust on Administrator" dimension in Table II. It has been understood that there is also a significant difference between perception levels of female staff ($\bar{X} = 3.29$) and that of male staff ($\bar{X} = 3.68$) according to $t(350) = -3.40$, $p < .05$. Male staff has higher perception compared to female ones in terms of Interpersonal trust, which creates a significant difference.

TABLE I
 AVERAGE AND STANDARD DEVIATION RESULTS BELONGING TO
 ORGANIZATIONAL TRUST SCALE OF STAFF AND INTERPERSONAL TRUST
 SCALE

	N	Min	Max	Average \bar{X}	S
Trust on Administrator	352	1,00	5,00	3,99	,76
Trust on the Organization Itself	352	1,00	5,00	3,59	,91
Interpersonal Trust	352	1,33	5,00	4,06	,72

TABLE II
INDEPENDENT SAMPLE T-TEST RESULTS OF DIFFERENCE BETWEEN ORGANIZATIONAL TRUST SCALE TO GENDER OF THE STAFF AND INTERPERSONAL TRUST SCALE PERCEPTIONS

	Gender	N	\bar{X}	S	t	Sd	P
Trust on Administrator	Female	78	3,91	,77	-1,08	350	,281
	Male	274	4,01	,76			
Trust on the Organization Itself	Female	78	3,29	,99	-3,40	350	,001*
	Male	274	3,68	,87			
Interpersonal Trust	Female	78	3,84	,80	-2,99	350	,003*
	Male	274	4,12	,69			

*p<,05

TABLE III
INDEPENDENT SAMPLE T-TEST RESULTS OF DIFFERENCE BETWEEN ORGANIZATIONAL TRUST SCALE TO MARITAL STATUS OF THE STAFF AND INTERPERSONAL TRUST SCALE PERCEPTIONS

	Marital Status	N	\bar{X}	S	T	Sd	P
Trust on Administrator	Married	287	4,00	,76	,61	350	,541
	Single	65	3,94	,75			
Trust on the Org. Itself	Married	287	3,62	,89	1,34	350	,182
	Single	65	3,45	,99			
Interpersonal Trust	Married	287	4,10	,69	2,21	350	,028*
	Single	65	3,88	,81			

*p<,05

Results of Independent Samples T test which has been carried out to determine differences of points obtained from scales according marital status variable of research staff are given in Table III. There is no significant difference in sub dimensions of "Trust on Administrator" and "Trust on the Organization Itself" in terms of gender variable ($p>0.05$). However, average of married staff is higher in both dimensions.

TABLE IV
INDEPENDENT SAMPLE T-TEST RESULTS OF DIFFERENCE BETWEEN ORGANIZATIONAL TRUST SCALE TO THE ORGANIZATION OF STAFF VARIABLE AND INTERPERSONAL TRUST SCALE PERCEPTIONS

	The Organization	N	\bar{X}	S	T	sd	P
Trust on Administrator	Metropolitan	92	3,95	,79	-,58	350	,562
	District	260	4,01	,75			
Trust on the Organization Itself	Metropolitan	92	3,42	,92	-2,0	350	,042
	District	260	3,65	,91			
Interpersonal Trust	Metropolitan	92	4,02	,67	-,56	350	,574
	District	260	4,07	,74			

*p<,05

On the other hand, there is a significant difference between perception level of married staff ($\bar{X}=4.10$) and that of single ones ($\bar{X}=3.88$) in "Interpersonal Trust Scale" according to $t(343)=2.21$, $p<.05$. The significant difference stems from the higher interpersonal perception level of married staff than single ones.

It is seen in Table IV that in "Trust on Administrator" sub dimension which is one of sub dimensions of "Organizational Trust Scale", there is no significant difference between perception levels of staff working in Metropolitan

Municipality ($\bar{X}=3.95$) and those in District Municipality ($\bar{X}=4.01$) considering $t(350)=-.58$, $p>.05$.

It has been also determined that perception levels of staff working in Metropolitan Municipality ($\bar{X}=3.42$) is higher than those in District Municipality ($\bar{X}=3.65$) in "Trust on the Organization Itself" dimension. Therefore, there happens a significant difference in favor of those working in Metropolitan Municipality.

Additionally, it has been understood that there is no significant difference between perception levels of staff working in Metropolitan Municipality ($\bar{X}=4.02$) and those in District Municipality ($\bar{X}=4.07$) considering $t(350)=-.56$, $p>.05$ in terms of "Interpersonal Trust Scale".

Analysis Results in Table V shows that staff working in laborer status has higher average points than civil servants in "Trust on Administrator" and "Trust on the Organization Itself" sub dimensions. One way analysis of variance points out that there is no significant difference between two sub dimensions of the scale and status of staff.

Perception levels of laborers ($\bar{X}=4.15$) are significantly higher than civil according to the points obtained from "Interpersonal Trust" scale results. ($t(350)=-2.16$, $p<.05$)

TABLE V
INDEPENDENT SAMPLE T-TEST RESULTS OF DIFFERENCE BETWEEN ORGANIZATIONAL TRUST SCALE TO THE STATUS OF STAFF AND INTERPERSONAL TRUST SCALE PERCEPTIONS

	Status	N	\bar{X}	S	t	Sd	P
Trust on Administrator	Civil servant	202	3,97	,73	-,57	350	,571
	Laborer	150	4,02	,81			
Trust on the Organization Itself	Civil servant	202	3,54	,87	-1,27	350	,206
	Laborer	150	3,66	,96			
Interpersonal Trust	Civil servant	202	3,98	,71	-2,16	350	,032*
	Laborer	150	4,15	,73			

*p<,05

Results of correlation points obtained from sub dimensions of Organizational Trust and Organizational Justice scales are given in Table VI.

TABLE VI
PEARSON CORRELATION RESULTS BELONGING TO PERCEPTION LEVELS OF MUNICIPALITY STAFF IN SUB DIMENSIONS OF "ORGANIZATIONAL TRUST SCALE", "INTERPERSONAL TRUST SCALE" AND "ORGANIZATIONAL JUSTICE PERCEPTION SCALE"

Organizational Justice		Trust on Administrator	Trust on the Organization Itself	Interpersonal Trust
Operative Justice	R	,56(**)	,61(**)	,55(**)
	P	,000	,000	,000
Distributive Justice	R	,28(**)	,39(**)	,33(**)
	P	,000	,000	,000
Interpersonal Justice	R	,54(**)	,43(**)	,50(**)
	P	,000	,000	,000
Informational Justice	r	,68(**)	,55(**)	,54(**)
	p	,000	,000	,000

It has been determined that there is a positive way and mid-level significant relation with $r=.56$, $p<0.05$ between Operative Justice and Trust on Administrator, sub dimensions

Organizational Justice Perception Scale. Also, there is a positive way and mid-level significance relation with $r=.55$, $p<0.05$ between "Operative Justice" and "Interpersonal Justice". Besides, there is a positive way and close to high level relation with $r=.61$, $p<0.05$ between "Operative Justice" and "Trust on the Organization Itself". That is to say, Operative justice perception accounts for 37% of trust on the organization itself ($r^2=0.37$ determination coefficient).

When "Interpersonal Justice" sub dimension data analyzed; it has been confirmed that there is a positive way and mid-level significant relation between it and others respectively; "Trust on Administrator" ($r=.54$), Trust on the Organization Itself ($r=.50$) and Interpersonal Trust Scale ($r=.50$).

According to the data obtained from the study, there is a parallel relation between "Informational Justice", one of the sub dimensions of Organizational Justice Perception Scale, and dimensions of Organizational Trust. When the results analyzed thoroughly, it has been determined that there is a positive way and high level significant relation between "Informational Justice" and staff perception belonging to "Trust on Administrator" according to $r=.68$, $p<0.05$. In other words, Informational Justice perception accounts for 46% of Trust on Administrator ($r^2=0.46$ determination coefficient).

Also, it has been understood that there is a positive way and mid-level significant relation between "Informational Justice" both staff's perception belonging to "Trust on the Organization Itself" according to $r=.55$, $p<0.05$ and Interpersonal Trust Scale and "Interpersonal Trust Scale" according to $r=.54$, $p<0.05$.

A positive way and significant relation between "Distributive Justice", one of the sub dimensions of Organizational Trust Scale, and "Trust on Administrator" and "Trust on the Organization Itself" are the sub dimensions of Organizational Trust Scale. However, it has been observed that this relation is at high levels in all dimensions.

VII. CONCLUSION

According to findings obtained from the data collection tool, municipality staff has high level of organizational trust perception. It has been determined that Interpersonal trust takes the first place with $\bar{x}=4.06$ average, trust on administrators with $\bar{x}=3.99$ and trust on the organization itself with $\bar{x}=3.59$ rate follow respectively with relation to the components of organizational trust (Table I). It is seen that municipality staff has high level of perceptions for organizational trust and it is more favorable in terms of "relations between employees".

The feeling of trust lies in the basis of raising employee satisfaction and performance. Only an employee with a feeling of trust on his organization can provide volunteer continuity, aim identification, high motivation and high performance [22]. In this sense, we can say that there is a reliable social structure, high level of staff communication, and productive and effective work system in municipalities according to staff's perception. In the consideration of the obtained data, unlike the structure in which administration looks down on its

employee, the municipalities studied on have a structure that enables continuity and productivity of the organization through their reliable intra organizational socio-psychological factors.

According to the analysis results, no difference between participants' Trust on Administrator perception and gender variable has been reported. On the other hand, there is a significant difference in favor of male staff in dimensions of Trust on the Organization itself and Interpersonal trust (Table II). Thus, it can be said that perception of male staff is more positive than female staff in terms of organizational trust.

That male staff have higher average in all dimensions and there is a significant difference to the detriment of female staff is thought provoking considering social gender reflections. Gender apartheid includes evaluations taking the gender into consideration rather than personal qualifications and performance and discrimination is done explicitly or implicitly [23]. According to ILO research reports concerning social gender apartheid in Turkey and in the world, women are discriminated against [24]. Therefore, both administrators and intra organizational implementations should be more attentive especially to women staff.

In related literature there are different results obtained from studies on organizational trust, such as; Bař and řentürk [25] suggest that organizational trust perceptions of primary school teachers show no difference in any sub dimensions in terms of gender variable ($p>.05$) and female teachers have a higher average than male ones. Also, Conn [26] points out that organizational trust varies according to gender but men trust less than women. In another study carried out by řokluk-Bökeođlu and Yılmaz [27], it is suggested that teachers shows no difference in terms of gender variable.

When the results of the relation between marital status variable and "Trust on Administrator" and "Trust on the Organization Itself" sub dimensions; it has been observed that married staff have higher level of perception but calculated results ($p>.05$) makes no difference for level of significance. On the other hand, it is seen that there is a significant difference in the data of "Interpersonal Trust Scale" in favor of married staff according to $t(343)=2.21$, $p<.05$ (Table III).

Durukan et al., Joseph and Winston support our study while Semerciođlu's study show similarities because of the difference stemming from being high in married ones and low in single ones in the organizational trust levels in terms of marital status [28]-[30].

When analyzed municipality staff's average points of organizational trusts components according to their organization, it has been determined that perception levels of staff working in District Municipalities and there is a significant difference in "Trust on the Organization Itself" sub dimension (Table IV).

It is expected in organizations having a strong trust ambiance that commitments of members to the organization, performance of them will raise and identification will get easier [31]. In this sense, especially metropolitan municipality administrators should take precautions in organizational processes and operations to raise trust of their staff.

Concerning status variable of participants, there is a significant difference in the points obtained from "Interpersonal Trust" scale ($t(350)=-2.16, p<.05$). This difference stems from the reason that staff working as civil servant have a lower perception for interpersonal trust ($\bar{x}=3.98$) than staff working as laborer ($\bar{x}=4.15$). Although average points of laborers is high at "Trust on Administrator" and "Trust on the Organization Itself" sub dimensions, results of one way analysis of variance point out no difference between statuses (Table V). Especially taken results of interpersonal trust into consideration, it is necessary to carry out activities which will help staff working as civil servant develop sensibility and trust on organization's communication ambiance and colleagues.

What is seen by public is the staff of local administrations which aim both to make people live in a quality way in its area and to raise satisfaction of their services. That's why, it will be possible with trust feeling both on colleagues and administrators, and commitment feeling to make use of human resources at the highest level undoubtedly. Though results of the study shows that participants have high level of organizational trust perception, something to be kept in mind is that staff workings as civil servant have low level of perception at all dimensions.

According to correlation analysis of findings, there is a positive relation between all dimensions of organizational justice perception and "Trust on Administrator", "Trust on the Organization Itself" and "Interpersonal Trust" (Table VI).

The most prominent of this positive way and high level relation is between "Operative Justice" and "Trust on the Organization Itself" sub dimensions ($r=.61, p<.05$), and "Informational Justice" and "Trust on Administrator" sub dimensions ($r=.68, p<.05$). It has also been found that there is a mid-level and same way significant relation between these two dimensions and other components of organizational trust. Also, there is a mid-level relation between "Interpersonal Justice" which is one of the other sub dimensions of organizational trust scale and Organizational trust dimensions while there is a low level significant relation between "Distributive Justice" and organizational trust (Table VI).

It has been understood from the results of the study that organizational justice implementations are important factors to raise trust feeling of staff on organization, administrator and colleagues, and Transactional justice which is made of "Operative Justice", "Informational Justice" and "Interpersonal Justice" is more prominent.

The literature supports the effect of "Interpersonal Justice" and "Informational Justice" which are dimensions of Transactional justice on trust. Ülker suggests that staff's perception for transactional justice affects their trust on the organization more than other justice perceptions and on administrator with the same values [32]. Therefore, administrators should pay attention and show consideration while they interact with their staff, and they also should regard and care their personal needs and rights.

In similar studies, it is seen that the higher staff have justice perception for their organization, the more they have

organizational trust [33], [34]. All these findings show that in such organizations having high level of justice perception there happens high level of trust feeling on administrator, organization and staff.

No matter how fast and innovative the changes of technologies occurring in today's business life are, success still depends on the use of human factor's skill and knowledge and how to use these in accordance with aims of the organization effectively and productively. This is only achieved by establishing a just order in the organization to gain trust of staff [35]. From this point of view, trust and justice concepts are closely relevant. It has been found in many studies on this area that justice affects trust and vice versa, and there is a two way relation [36].

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